

AZO-FUNCTIONALIZED METAL-ORGANIC POLYHEDRA FOR THE REMOVAL OF PFOA FROM AQUEOUS SOLUTIONS

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ABSTRACT

Perfluorooctanoic acid (PFOA) has been extensively studied in recent years due to its widespread distribution in aquatic environments, persistent chemical structure, and potential threats to human health. We synthesized MOP-5, a metal-organic polyhedron functionalized with an azo group. The structure was characterized by single-crystal X-ray diffraction (SC-XRD), mass spectrometry (MS), and infrared spectroscopy (IR). The adsorption process of PFOA by the MOP-5 was monitored via ¹⁹F-NMR spectroscopy. The results indicate that MOP-5 exhibit excellent PFOA adsorption performance, with maximum adsorption capacities of 811 mg/g.

INTRODUCTION

Perfluorooctanoic acid (PFOA) consists of a carboxyl group and a long carbon chain in which all hydrogen atoms are replaced by fluorine atoms. It is widely used in coatings, surfactants, leather, and firefighting foams.^[1] PFOA has gained attention as an emerging contaminant in recent years due to its persistent C–F bonds, which render its resistance to natural degradation and wide distribution in water resources.^[2] Due to its strong physiological toxicity to humans.^[3,4] various methods.^[5] such as bioremediation,^[6] electrocoagulation^[7], and electrochemical degradation.^[8] have been developed to remove PFOA from aqueous solutions. However, adsorption remains the most widely used approach due to its operational simplicity. Regarding adsorbent selection, materials such as activated carbon,^[9] metal-organic frameworks (MOFs),^[10] and covalent organic frameworks

(COFs).^[11] have been utilized for PFOA adsorption, though their adsorption capacities are generally limited. We note that metal-organic polyhedra (MOPs), as a class of porous materials extensively studied in recent years, also hold significant potential for PFOA adsorption, yet they remain relatively underutilized in this field.^[12]

Metal-organic polyhedra (MOPs) are polyhedral cage-like structures formed by metal clusters as vertices and organic molecules as linkers. Unlike the extended network structure of MOFs, MOP molecules are discrete in the crystalline state. MOPs possess well-defined geometric structures, tunable cavities, and permanent porosity.^[12] They have been widely applied in gas separation,^[13] and storage,^[14] catalysis,^[15] and structural analysis,^[16] and also demonstrate potential for PFOA adsorption. In this work, we designed and synthesized MOP-5. The structure was analyzed and verified using methods SC-XRD, NMR, MS, and IR. Concurrently, the adsorption performance of MOP-5 for PFOA in aqueous solution was investigated. The adsorption process was monitored by ¹⁹F-NMR. Possible interactions between the MOP and PFOA during adsorption were examined by IR. This work expands the variety of PFOA adsorbents and broadens the potential application scope of MOPs, aiming to provide insights for the structural design and selection of adsorbents for PFOA removal.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Synthesis of MOP-5

In contrast to NUT-101^[17], a novel synthetic route was developed (Fig.1). A mixture of Cp₂ZrCl₂ (0.06 mmol, 17.5 mg) and azobenzene-4,4'-dicarboxylic acid (AZDA) (0.03 mmol, 8.1 mg) was dissolved in a solvent mixture (5 mL *N,N'*-dimethyl formamide (DMF) and 0.2 mL deionized water) by ultrasonication. The solution was then sealed in a Teflon-lined autoclave and heated at 65 °C for 8 hours in an oven. Subsequently, the temperature was gradually lowered to room temperature at a rate of 10 °C/h. Orange block-shaped crystals of MOP-5 were obtained with a yield of 6.3%.

MOP-5 synthesis:

Fig.1: Synthetic scheme of MOP-5.

Structural Characterization

MOP-5 crystallizes in the monoclinic crystal system with the space group $P2_1/c$. (Fig.2a) At its vertices, cyclopentadienyl ligands coordinate to zirconium atoms, forming a $[Cp_3Zr_3(\mu_3-O)_2(\mu_2-OH)_2(COO)_3]$ trinuclear cluster. This cluster connects with the azobenzene-4,4'-dicarboxylic acid ligand, assembling a capsule-shaped, columnar metal-organic polyhedron. The size of the cylinder-like cavity is 16.2×4.3 Å. PLATON calculations reveal that the total potential solvent-accessible volume of MOP-5 is 1967.3 Å³, corresponding to 23.2% of the total unit cell volume (8470.6 Å³).

The ¹H NMR spectrum of MOP-5 (400 MHz, CD₃OD) (Fig.2b): δ 7.85 (d, $J = 8.0$ Hz, 12H, Ph-H), 7.56 (d, $J = 8.0$ Hz, 12H, Ph-H), 6.68 (s, 30H, Cp-H). MS analysis revealed peaks corresponding to the positively charged molecular species $[M-2Cl^- -H^+]^{1+}$ at m/z 1876.8120 for MOP-5 (Fig. 2c). In the IR spectrum of MOP-5 (Fig. 2d), a weak absorption band at 3403 cm⁻¹ is assigned to the -OH stretching vibration. The band at 1591 cm⁻¹ corresponds to the C=C stretching vibration of the cyclopentadienyl ring, while the absorption near 1535 cm⁻¹ is attributed to the in-plane bending vibration of aromatic C-H bonds. A sharp band at 1421 cm⁻¹ is associated with the C-O stretching vibration of the azobenzene-4,4'-dicarboxylic acid (AZDA) ligand. Notably, the disappearance of the characteristic C=O stretching band around 1700 cm⁻¹ confirms the successful coordination of the carboxylate groups of the AZDA ligand with the zirconium ions. Collectively, these data confirm the successful synthesis of MOP-5.

Fig 2. Characterization of MOP-5. a. Crystal structure of MOP-5. b. The ¹H NMR spectrum of MOP-5 (400 MHz, CD₃OD) c. MS of MOP-5. d. FT-IR of MOP-5.

Adsorption of PFOA

MOP-5 solids were placed in a 1000 ppm PFOA solution. After 24 hours, it was found that the PFOA molecules were completely removed from the supernatant, demonstrating the excellent adsorption capacity of MOP as evidenced by the absence of fluorine signal in the ¹⁹F-NMR (Fig. 3a). Based on this result, we proceeded to investigate the adsorption kinetics of MOP-5 (Fig. 3b). After 24 hours of adsorption, the maximum adsorption capacity of MOP-5 reached 811 mg/g. The adsorption process was fitted using pseudo- first- order and pseudo- second- order kinetic models.^[18]

The pseudo-first-order kinetic model

$$\ln(q_e - q_t) = \ln(q_e) - k_1 t$$

The pseudo-second-order kinetic model

$$\frac{t}{q_t} = \frac{1}{k_2 q_e^2} + \frac{t}{q_e}$$

q_e: adsorption capacity at equilibrium. **q_t**: adsorption capacity at time **t**. **t**: adsorption time. **k₁**, **k₂**: rate constants of the two kinetic models.

The pseudo-first-order kinetic model describes an adsorption process that is primarily influenced by the initial concentration,^[19] whereas the pseudo-second-order kinetic model indicates that the adsorption process is governed by the availability of active sites on the adsorbent surface.^[20] Based on the Adjusted R² values, MOP-5 is better described by the pseudo-second-order kinetic model. The adsorption rate constants for MOP-5 are 2.05 × 10⁻³ g·mg⁻¹·h⁻¹, respectively (Table1). These results suggest that MOP-5 can rapidly adsorb PFOA, demonstrating strong binding affinity.

Fig 3. a. Complete removal of PFOA from solution by MOP-5 as indicated by ¹⁹F NMR. Trifluoroethanol (TEF) was used as an internal standard. **b.** Kinetic analysis of PFOA adsorption by MOP-5.

Table 1. Adsorption Kinetics of MOP-5 for PFOA Removal

		MOP-5
Maximum Adsorption Capacity for PFOA (mg/g)		811
Pseudo-first-order kinetic modeling	R-Square	0.9124
	R-Square	0.99059
Pseudo-second-order kinetic modeling	Adsorption Rate Constant ($\text{g}\cdot\text{mg}^{-1}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$)	2.05×10^{-3}

The composites MOP-5@PFOA were analyzed using IR (Fig. 4). In the spectrum of MOP-5@PFOA, where the peaks at 1536 cm^{-1} and 1421 cm^{-1} are characteristic of MOP-5, indicating that it retained structure after the adsorption of PFOA. The absorption at 1147 cm^{-1} is attributed to the C–C–C bending vibration of PFOA, while the peaks at 1208 cm^{-1} and 1240 cm^{-1} arise from the C–F stretching vibrations of PFOA. These IR results demonstrate the successful adsorption of PFOA by MOP-5.

Fig. 4 FTIR spectrum of MOP-5@PFOA.

CONCLUSION

In this research, we synthesized MOP-5, a zirconium-based metal-organic polyhedra (MOP), using cyclopentadienyl-based zirconium clusters as polyhedral vertices. MOP-5 incorporates an azo bond (N=N) in its organic ligand, and a new synthetic route was independently developed for its preparation. MOP-5 exhibited high adsorption capacity for perfluorooctanoic acid (PFOA). Specifically, MOP-5 showed an adsorption capacity of 811

mg/g with a rate constant of $2.05 \times 10^{-3} \text{ g} \cdot \text{mg}^{-1} \cdot \text{h}^{-1}$. This work expands the application scope of MOPs, enriches the variety of adsorbents available for PFOA removal.

Experimental section

$\text{Cp}_2 \text{ZrCl}_2$, azobenzene-4,4'-dicarboxylic acid (AZDA), *N,N'*-dimethyl formamide (DMF), Perfluorooctanoic acid (PFOA), trifluoroethanol (TEF) were purchased from Shanghai Bidepharm Co., Ltd. (Shanghai, China). Deuterium oxide ($\text{D}_2 \text{O}$), MeOH-d_4 were obtained from Energy Chemicals (Anhui, China).

Single crystal X-ray diffraction experiment: Single-crystal X-ray measurements were performed on a Rigaku-Oxford SuperNova diffractometer. A high-quality single crystal of the synthesized MOP was selected and mounted on a diffractometer. Data were collected at a controlled temperature using $\text{Cu K}\alpha$ radiation ($\lambda = 1.54178 \text{ \AA}$). After absorption correction, the structure was solved with SHELXTL-97 and refined with Olex 2 software. All non-hydrogen atoms were refined anisotropically, and hydrogen atoms bound to carbon were placed at calculated positions. Disordered solvent molecules were treated using the SQUEEZE routine implemented in the PLATON software package.

Mass Spectrometry: Matrix-assisted laser desorption/ionization time-of-flight mass spectrometry (MALDI-TOF-MS) was performed using a Bruker ultrafleXtreme MALDI-TOF-MS instrument. 2,5-Dihydroxybenzoic acid (CHCA) was used as the matrix during the experiment.

NMR spectroscopy: Approximately 2 mg of the MOP sample was dissolved in deuterated methanol (MeOH-d_4). ^1H NMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker AV400 MHz NMR spectrometer, with tetramethylsilane (TMS, $\delta = 0 \text{ ppm}$) used as the internal reference.

FT-IR spectroscopy: A small amount of the dried sample was thoroughly mixed with KBr, ground, and pressed into a pellet. A separate pellet of pure KBr was prepared for background scanning. After the instrument was properly warmed up, spectral data were collected over the range of 4000 to 400 cm^{-1} . Baseline correction was applied after scanning.

PFOA Adsorption Experiment: The synthesized MOP-5 were washed three times with the DMF, followed by three additional washes with acetone. They were then vacuum-dried at 70°C for two hours before use. 5 mg of MOP-5 solid was added to 1 ml of 1000 ppm PFOA- $\text{D}_2 \text{O}$ solution and left to stand for 24 hours. Then, 500 μl of the supernatant

was collected, and 1 μ l of trifluoroethanol was added as an internal standard. The PFOA content in the supernatant was monitored via ^{19}F NMR on a Bruker Avance-400 NMR spectrometer.

PFOA Adsorption Kinetics Experiment: 2 mg of the solid MOP sample was added to 1 mL of a 3 mg/mL PFOA-D₂O solution. After standing for a specified duration, 500 μ l of the supernatant was collected, and 1 μ l of trifluoroethanol was added as an internal standard. The PFOA content in the supernatant was monitored via ^{19}F NMR on a Bruker Avance-400 NMR spectrometer.

REFERENCE

1. Glüge, J., Scheringer, M., Cousins, I. T., DeWitt, J. C., Goldenman, G., Herzke, D., Lohmann, R., Ng, C. A., Trier, X., & Wang, Z. An overview of the uses of per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS). *Environ. Sci.: Processes Impacts*, 2020; 22(12): 2345-2373. <https://doi.org/10.1039/D0EM00291G>
2. Garnick, L., Massarsky, A., Mushnick, A., Hamaji, C., Scott, P., & Monnot, A. An evaluation of health-based federal and state PFOA drinking water guidelines in the United States. *Sci. Total Environ.*, 2021; 761: 144107. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2020.144107>
3. Liang, L.Y., Pan, Y.L., Bin, L.H., Liu, Y., Huang, W.J., Li, R., & Lai, K.P. Immunotoxicity mechanisms of perfluorinated compounds PFOA and PFOS. *Chemosphere*, 2022; 291(Pt2): 132892. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2021.132892>
4. EFSA CONTAM Panel (EFSA Panel on Contaminants in the Food Chain), Scientific Opinion on the risk to human health related to the presence of perfluorooctane sulfonic acid and perfluorooctanoic acid in food. *EFSA J.*, 2018; 16(12): 5194. <https://doi.org/10.2903/j.efsa.2018.5194>
5. Leung, S.C.E., Shukla, P., Chen, D., Eftekhari, E., An, H., Zare, F., Ghasemi, N., Zhang, D., Nguyen, N.-T. & Li, Q. Emerging technologies for PFOS/PFOA degradation and removal: A review. *Sci. Total Environ.*, 2022; 827: 153669. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2022.153669>
6. Chetverikov, S.P. & Loginov, O.N. A New *Ensifer adhaerens* Strain M1 is Capable of Transformation of Perfluorocarboxylic Acids. *Microbiology*, 2019; 88: 115–117. <https://doi.org/10.1134/S0026261718060085>

7. Yang, B., Han, Y.N., Yu, G., Zhuo, Q.F., Deng, S.B., Wu, J.H. & Zhang, P.X. Efficient removal of perfluoroalkyl acids (PFAAs) from aqueous solution by electrocoagulation using iron electrode. *Chem. Eng. J.*, 2016; 303: 384-390. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2016.06.011>
8. Garcia-Costa, A.L., Savall, A., Zazo, J.A., Casas, J.A. & Groenen Serrano, K. On the Role of the Cathode for the Electro-Oxidation of Perfluorooctanoic Acid. *Catalysts*, 2020; 10: 902. <https://doi.org/10.3390/catal10080902>
9. Zhang, D., Luo, Q., Gao, B., Chiang, S.Y.D., Woodward, D. & Huang, Q.G. Sorption of perfluorooctanoic acid, perfluorooctane sulfonate and perfluoroheptanoic acid on granular activated carbon. *Chemosphere*, 2016; 144 2336-2342. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2015.10.124>
10. Liang, R.R., Xu, S.Q., Han, Z.S., Yang, Y.H., Wang, K.Y., Huang, Z.H., Rushlow, J., Cai, P.Y., Samori, P. & Zhou, H.C. Exceptionally High Perfluorooctanoic Acid Uptake in Water by a Zirconium-Based Metal-Organic Framework through Synergistic Chemical and Physical Adsorption. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2024; 146: 9811-9818. <https://doi.org/10.1021/jacs.3c14487>
11. Ji, W.J., Xiao, L.L. & Ling, Y.H. Removal of GenX and Perfluorinated Alkyl Substances from Water by Amine-Functionalized Covalent Organic Frameworks. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2018; 140: 12677-12681. <https://doi.org/10.1021/jacs.8b06958>
12. Mu, C.Q., Wang, H.D., Wang, X.Y., Zhou, Y.Z., Zhang, L., Jian, S.J., Guo, Z.T., Li, Z.K., Wang, M. & Zhang, M.M. Pyrene-Based Multicomponent Metallacages for Highly Efficient Adsorption and Photocatalytic Degradation of Perfluorooctanoic Acid. *ACS Nano*, 2025; 19(43): 37943-37953. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsnano.5c12506>
13. Yang, Y., Pang, B., Zeng, W., Zhang, M., Guo, Q., Cao, S., Wang, M., Hu, Q., Yu, H. & He, Z. Enhance gas-separation efficiency of mixed matrix membranes by lamellarly arranged metal-organic polyhedron. *Nano Res.*, 2023; 16: 11450-11454. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12274-023-5874-9>
14. Hong, S., Oh, M., Park, M., Yoon, J.W., Chang, J.S. & Lah, M.S. Large H₂ storage capacity of a new polyhedron-based metal-organic framework with high thermal and hygroscopic stability. *Chem. Commun.*, 2009; (43): 6717-6719. <https://doi.org/10.1039/B909250A>
15. Takezawa, H., Iizuka, K. & Fujita, M. Selective Synthesis and Functionalization of an Acyclic Methylene-Bridged-Arene Trimer in a Cage. *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, 2024; 63: e202319140. <https://doi.org/10.1002/anie.202319140>

16. He, W., Yu, Y., Iizuka, K. & Fujita, M. Supramolecular coordination cages as crystalline sponges through a symmetry mismatch strategy. *Nat. Chem.*, 2025; 17: 653-662. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41557-025-01766-1>
17. Jiang, Y., Tan, P., Qi, S.C., Gu, C., Peng, S.S., Wu, F., Liu, X.Q. & Sun, L.B. Breathing Metal–Organic Polyhedra Controlled by Light for Carbon Dioxide Capture and Liberation. *CCS Chem.* 2020; 2: 1724-1736. <https://doi.org/10.31635/ccschem.020.202000314>
18. Sini, K., Bourgeois, D., Idouhar, M., Carboni, M. & Meyer, D. Metal–organic framework sorbents for the removal of perfluorinated compounds in an aqueous environment. *New J. Chem.* 2018; 42: 17889-17894. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C8NJ03312A>
19. Azizian, S. & Yahyaei, B. Adsorption of 18-crown-6 from aqueous solution on granular activated carbon: A kinetic modeling study. *J. Colloid Interface Sci.* 2006; 299: 112-115. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcis.2006.01.058>
20. Liu, Y. New insights into pseudo-second-order kinetic equation for adsorption. *Colloids Surf., A* 2008; 320: 275-278. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.colsurfa.2008.01.032>